

APPROACHES TO THE ESSENCE OF LOGISTICS STRUCTURES AND FORMATION OF LOGISTICS CHAIN

Mirsodikov Abdulla Tursunaliyevych

Senior lecturer of Fergana State University "Economics and Service"

Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7917957>

Abstract: Currently, in the world, scientific research is being carried out in priority areas such as digitalization of the construction industry, improvement of the integrated development system of settlements, creation of new technological types of services in the logistic chains of the construction industry, and increasing their share in the GDP by optimizing costs in the logistic chains.

Key words: building materials, logistics, logistics systems, logistics chain

The term "Logistics" is derived from the Greek word and means "the art of calculation" or "the art of thinking, calculating". In ancient Athens, there was a special position, the "logistic", whose officials were appointed annually by lot, and whose duties included checking the reports of other officials.

The word "logistics" exists in all major European languages, but has different meanings. The term "Logistics" was used by famous scientists, philosophers, and military leaders in their works. The famous German mathematician G.V. Leibniz (1646-1716) used this term in the sense of "mathematical logic". In 1884, the American Naval Institute introduced the concept of "logistics" for the needs of navigation. In 1904, the definition of logistics as mathematical logic was confirmed at the Philosophical Congress in Geneva.

The principles of logistics were widely developed in the field of logistics of the American army during World War II. Military industry, rear and frontline supply bases, clear interaction of transport to provide the army with weapons, fuel and food in the right amount and in time, as well as civilian made it possible to solve supply and marketing activities of enterprises.

Since the end of the 20th century, the science of "Logistics" has been performing the function of an economic direction, including supply, production, sales, transportation, information logistics, etc. Each of these areas of human activity has been sufficiently studied, but the novelty of the logistics approach is the integration of these areas of activity to achieve the desired result with minimal time, material resources and financial resources. Thus, logistics is designed to meet the needs of consumers as much as possible. Logistics combines supply, production, sales, transportation and other areas of economic activity, planning, control and transportation, management, storage and other tangible and intangible operations are considered in logistics as a science.

The characteristics of chains consisting of logistics systems are as follows:

- different forms of ownership and organizational-legal form;
- differences in the nature and purpose of the activity;
- different capabilities, concentration and types of used technological equipment and consumed resources;

Logistics systems can be divided into micro, macro and meso logistics systems according to the scope of their activities and goals (Fig. 1).

Micrologistics systems are divided into three types of systems depending on their place in the activity of enterprises:

1. Domestic logistics systems.
2. External logistics systems.
3. Integrated logistics systems.

1- picture. Classification of logistics systems

Macrologistics systems are a management system of large economic flows, which include mediation, trade and transport organizations and enterprises of various divisions, as well as the infrastructure of the economy of a specific country or group of countries. Macrologistic systems can be created to solve commercial, social, economic, ecological, scientific and other tasks at the administrative-territorial level. Corporations form the basis of mesologistics systems. Corporations form the middle (meso) connection of the economy, activities are planned inside corporations, and the market is the place where final products are presented outside. The management activity of corporations as a single system is mesologistics based on the use of global networks. The intensity of economic flows is increasing based on the

integration of technologies between suppliers, trade intermediaries, purchasing enterprises and construction companies. They are reflected in:

- to reduce the duration of permanent construction, simultaneously focused construction production, rationalization market need initiative, increase the life cycle of real estate and reduce the costs of construction production;
- changing the demands of consumers related to the design of new serial houses and the development of new construction products;
- reorientation of construction organizations from narrow functional construction to solve the problems of customers who use various combinations of construction materials, forms and methods of commodity exchange, which expands the boundaries of potential pairing of construction technologies;
- change the level of industrialization of construction, unification of basic construction technologies;
- the economic independence of economic entities participating in the material and technical support of construction encourages them to use the logistic potential of horizontal and conglomerate integration even more.

The successful use of the logistics approach in the construction industry is classified into the following group of factors:

1. Organizational factors. The scope of coordinating the distribution of resources in construction between contractors, production stages, construction objects, etc. implies the creation of appropriate organizational management structures. The existence of a single management (management system) creates general standards for decision-making and implementation aimed at increasing the efficiency of economic flows, forms the informational integration of management procedures.
2. Technological factors. It requires constant and full loading of production capacities in the construction sector, integration during construction processes, unity of production and service operations.
3. Economic factors. The interdependence of the financial and economic results of the activities of all participants in the construction industry and their impact on the final economic results of production in the construction industry serve as the basis for creating a logistics system. The general task of the production logistics system in the field of construction is to ensure the completeness, timeliness and cost-effectiveness of the delivery of construction materials to the construction site.

The logistics chain in the construction industry is applied to the activities of enterprises, leads to the formation of an integrated logistics system, and as a result ensures the formation of integrated effects:

- coordination of all processes of commodity movements, including purchase of building materials, packaging, management of fixed assets and work-in-progress, production management;
- integration of materials management and control functions (management integration);
- integration of technological processes of the construction company and its partners (technological integration);
- integration of material and information flows;

- formation as an integrated logistics system, which includes the formation of a reasonable organizational structure (organizational integration) for the company's business goals..

References:

1. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Совершенствование механизмов управления затратами в логистических цепях строительной отрасли // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2022. Т. 8. №2. -231-239- б.
2. Mirsodikov A.T. Improving the management process of logistic chain activity in construction // Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA) Vol. 3 No. 03. March, 2022.
3. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Рақамлашув шароитида қурилиш соҳасида логистика занжирини бошқариш // Хоразм Маъмун академияси ахборотномаси. – 2022. №1. 93–97-б. (08.00.00 №21).
4. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳаси логистик занжирларида харажатларни бошқариш механизми такомиллаштириш // “Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. 2022 й., №1. -61–72-б. (№00057).
5. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасини бошқариш тизимларида логистикадан фойдаланиш хусусиятлари // Бизнес-эксперт. Бизнес-Daily медиа. 2021, №10. - 43–47-б. (08.00.00 №3).
6. Mirsodikov A.T. Improving logistics cost management in the construction sector // International Conference on Developments in Education, Sciences and Humanities Hosted from Hamburg, Germany. 2022, Mart. -15-16 б.
7. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Анализ деятельности логистических цепочек в строительной отрасли Узбекистана и тенденций на рынке услуг “Наука Сегодня Вызовы и Решения” материалы международной научно-практической конференции. Вологда, 2022. -34-37 б.
8. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sohasi mikrologistik zanzirlarida xarajatlarni boshqarish. “Ўзбекистон банк тизимини трансформация қилишнинг фундаментал асослари ва механизми такомиллаштириш” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари тўплами. Тошкент, Молия, 2021. -267-270 б.
9. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sanoatini rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning o‘rni. “Иқтисодиётни рақамлаштириш шароитида иқтисодиётдаги таркибий ўзгаришлар: муаммолар, ечимлар ва истиқболлар” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари тўплами. Фарғона, ФарПИ, 2021. - 134-137 б.
10. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасида логистика харажатларини бошқаришнинг интеграциялашган тизимини такомиллаштириш. “Sanoat va xizmat ko‘rsatish sohaslarining raqamli transformatsiyasi: tendensiyalar, boshqaruv, strategiyalar” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to‘plami. Buxoro, BDU, 2022. -119-123 б.
11. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасида логистика харажатларини бошқаришнинг тизимини такомиллаштириш. “Учинчи ренессанс шакллантириш шароитида хизмат кўрсатиш ва таълим хизматлари соҳаларини

ривожлантириш муаммолари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. Самарқанд. СамИСИ, 2022. 138-142 б

12. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳаси кластерларида логистик жараёнларни бошқаришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш “Sanoat va xizmat ko’rsatish sohalarining raqamli transformatsiyasi: tendensiyalar, boshqaruv, strategiyalar” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to’plami. Buxoro, BDU, 2022. 184-188 b.

13. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳаси кластерларида логистик жараёнларни бошқариш. “Globallashuv sharoitida tadbirkorlik va kichik biznesni rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to’plami. Namangan. Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti 15-16-aprel, 2022-yil. 39-42-b.

14. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасида логистик фаолиятни бошқариш жараёнларини такомиллаштириш. “Реал сектор соҳаси иқтисодиётини ривожлантиришнинг илмий асослари ва муаммолари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. Самарқанд. СамИСИ, 2022. 182-187 б.

15. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасини бошқариш тизимларида логистикадан фойдаланишнинг ўзига хос хусусиятлари. “Реал сектор соҳаси иқтисодиётини ривожлантиришнинг илмий асослари ва муаммолари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. Самарқанд. СамИСИ, 2022. 28-32 б.

16. Мирсодиқов А.Т. Қурилиш соҳасида логистик занжирлари ва уларни бошқариш хусусиятлари “Учинчи ренессансни шакллантириш шароитида хизмат кўрсатиш ва таълим хизматлари соҳаларини ривожлантириш муаммолари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллари. Самарқанд. СамИСИ, 2022. 163-166 б.

17. Mirsodikov A.T. Improving the cost management mechanism in the construction industry logistic chains // INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION International scientific-online conference. Part 6. May 23. 2022. 265-272-б.

18. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sohasini rivojlanishida investitsiyalarni o’rni va ahamiyati. “Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsiya faoliyatini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari” mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasining materiallari to’plami. Toshkent, Moilya, 2021. 534-537 б.

19. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sohasida innovatsiya loyihalarini iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash masalalari. “Ўзбекистон банк тизимини трансформация қилишнинг фундаментал асослари ва механизмини такомиллаштириш” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари то’плами. Тошкент. Молия, 2021. -385-388 б.

20. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sohasini rivojlanishida logistik xarajatlarni ahamiyati “Ўзбекистонда миллий статистика тизимини такомиллаштиришнинг устувор йўналишлари” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари то’плами. Тошкент. Молия, 2021. -309-314 б.

21. Mirsodiqov A.T. Qurilish sohasida kadrlar salohiyati va uni boshqaruvining ahamiyati “Ўзбекистон банк тизимини трансформация қилишнинг фундаментал асослари ва механизмини такомиллаштириш” мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари то’плами. Тошкент. Молия, 2021. -267-270 б.

22. Mirsodiqov A.T. Raqamlashuv sharoitida qurilish sohasida logistika xarajatlarni boshqarish. "Ўзбекистонда миллий статистика тизимини такомиллаштиришнинг устувор йўналишлари" мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференциясининг материаллари тўплами. Тошкент. Молия, 2021. -309-314 б.
23. Mirsodiqov A.T. "Qurilish sohasi logistik zanjirlarida xarajatlarni boshqarish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish" Iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi avtoreferati. – Toshkent. 2022.13-sentyabr. 57-bet
24. Мирсодиков, А.Т. (2021). Активация инвестиций в экономическое развитие: современные тенденции и опыт зарубежных стран. *Cognitio rerum*, 10, 32-35.
25. Tursunaliyevich, M.A. (2021). Iqtisodiy tarmoqlarni rivojlanishida xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyati. *Development issues of innovative economy in the agricultural sector*, 194.
26. Мирсодиков, А., & Черданцев, В. П. (2020). Роль маркетинговой стратегии в повышении конкурентоспособности образовательных услуг. информационные системы и коммуникативные технологии в современном образовательном процессе, 50-56
27. Мирсодиков, А.Т. (2021). Важность привлечения инвестиций в отрасли национальной экономики. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 7(10), 329-33
28. Mirzaev A. T. Estimation of the prospects for the use of recreational facilities in the market of tourism services // *Наука сегодня: вызовы, перспективы и возможности [Текст]*. – 2018. – С. 76.
29. Mirzaev A.T. Туристик-рекреация кластерларини бошқаришда инновацион салоҳиятнинг ресурс компонентини баҳолаш услубиёти "Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar" ilmiy elektron jurnali. № 4, iyul-avgust, 2020 yil. 390-401 б.
30. Мирзаев А. Т. Рекреацион туризм хизматлари бозорини ривожлантириш орқали аҳоли бандлигини таъминлаш хусусиятлари // *Бизнес-Daily медиа [Текст]*. 2018. №11. 63-66 б.
31. Мирзаев А. Т. Ўзбекистонда туристик-рекреация корхоналари фаолиятини бошқаришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш // *Бизнес-Daily медиа [Текст]*. 2020. №1. 62-65
32. Мирзаев А.Т. Методологические основы развития и повышения конкурентоспособности туристско-рекреационной деятельности// *Бюллетень науки и практики*. 2021. Т. 7. №10. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/71/33>. Нижневартовск, Россия. С.283-293
33. Mirzaev Abdullajon Topilovich. (2021). Economic evaluation of multiplicative efficiency on the basis of generalized indicators of resource components in tourist recreation activities. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(6), 107-114. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrds/article/view/1004>
34. Мирзаев А.Т. Туризм-рекреацияси хизматлар бозоридида рақамлаштиришнинг ялпи талаб ўзгаришига таъсири таҳлили // *Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар*. - 2021, №3. 3/2021 (№ 00053). 386-397 б. <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>.